

MECHANICS OF RANDOM STRUCTURE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Considered is a nonlinear elastic composite medium, which consists of a homogeneous matrix containing a homogeneous a statistically uniform random set of ellipsoidal inclusions. A multiparticle effective field method (EFM) is developed to estimate the macroscopic properties of the physically nonlinear elastic composites. When linearisation of nonlinear functions takes place, physically consistent assumption about dependency of these function from average by component's values of the second invariant of the stress deviator is applied. The exact estimates for the second moments of the stress (which are obtained by autor early) are used.

Keywords: random structure, physically nonlinear elastic composites.

1. INTRODACTION

The new multiparticle effective field method (EFM) has been proposed recently (references may be found in the survey of Buryachenko and Parton [1] and [2],[3]). EFM is based on the theory of functions of random variables and Green's functions, does not make use of a number of hypotheses which form the basis of the traditional one-particle methods related to this trend. EFM includes as particular cases well-know methods of mechanics of highly heterogeneous media. Standart methods for nonlinear problems of successive approximation are used equally with variational estimates (Willis and Taldom [4]) in relation to random structure composites with the solution by linearized problems at each stage. It is, for example, known the secant modulus conception and hypotheses for homogeneity in components of the deformations (Tandon and Weng [5], Buryachenko and Lipanov [6]). Because of significant inhomogeneity of stress fields in the components (especially in matrices), there exists physical inconsistency of such a linearisation, which will be shown below by the example of porous medium.

In this paper at each step the linearized problem is solved with the help of EFM. What is more, when linearization of non-linear functions takes place, physically consistent assumption about dependency of these functions from average by component's values of the second

invariant of the stress deviator is applied. In doing so the exact estimates of Parton and Buryachenko [7] in relation to the average in volume of anisotropic components single-point second moments of the stress fields are used.

2. PRELIMINARIES

The paper discusses a certain presentative macrodomain w with a characteristic function W containing a set $X=(v_i)$ of inclusions v_i with characteristic functions V_i . The local strain tensor ε which is required to satisfy the compatibility relation

$$\varepsilon = \nabla u \quad (2.1)$$

in terms of the displacement u , is related to the stress σ , satisfying the equilibrium equations

$$\nabla \sigma = 0 \quad (2.2)$$

via the constitutive relation

$$\sigma(x) = L(x, \varepsilon) \varepsilon(x), \quad (2.3)$$

where ∇ is the operator of symmetrised gradient; $L(x)$ is a fourth-order tensor for nonlinear elasticity modulus. Here, we will further assume that the dependence $L(x, \varepsilon) \sim \varepsilon(x)$ is only through two of the invariants

$$\varepsilon_0 = \varepsilon_{ii} / 3, \quad e^2 = 4\vartheta_{ij} \vartheta_{ij} / 3, \quad (2.4)$$

where $\vartheta_{ij} \equiv \varepsilon_{ij} - \varepsilon_0 \delta_{ij}$.

In particular, for the strain potential

$$W(\varepsilon) = (3k + 4\mu) \varepsilon_0^2 / 2 + 3\mu e^2 / 4 + 3\gamma e^4 / 4 \quad (2.5)$$

we are obtain from expression $\sigma = \partial W / \partial \varepsilon$

$$L_{ijkl}(\varepsilon) = C_{ijkl} + \psi_{ijkl}(\varepsilon), \quad (2.6)$$

$$C = (3k, 2\mu) \equiv 3kN_1 + 2\mu N_2, \quad \psi(\varepsilon) = \gamma e^2 N_2,$$

$$N_{1ijkl} = \delta_{ij} \delta_{kl} / 3, \quad N_{2ijkl} = (\delta_{ik} \delta_{jl} + \delta_{il} \delta_{jk} - 2\delta_{ij} \delta_{kl} / 3) / 2.$$

Here k and μ are the bulk and shear modulus, γ is a nonlinear parameter.

The tensor of material properties $f \equiv f^{(0)} + f_1(x)$ ($f = L, k, \mu, \gamma$) are assumed to be constant in the matrix $v_0 = w \setminus v$ ($v \equiv Uv_k, k = 1, 2, \dots$)

$f(x) = f^{(0)}$ and in each v_k ($k=1, 2, \dots$) $f(x) = f^{(0)} + f_1^{(k)}$; both here and below the upper index of materials properties tensor put in parentheses, shows the number of the respective components. The method of estimation of secant modulus $L^{s(i)} = \text{const}$ ($i=0, 1, \dots$) will be presented below.

We assume that the phases are perfectly bounded, so that the displacements and traction components of the stress are continuous across the interphase boundaries.

It is assumed that the representative domain w contains a statistically large number of inclusions v_k ; all the random qualities under discussion are described by statistically homogeneous ergodic random field and, thereby, the ensemble averaging could be replaced by volume averaging

$$\langle (\cdot) \rangle = \bar{v}^{-1} \int (\cdot) V(x) dx, \quad \langle (\cdot) \rangle_k = \bar{v}_k^{-1} \int (\cdot) V_k(x) dx, \quad (k=0, 1, \dots) \quad (2.7)$$

The bar available above the region represents its measure, $\bar{v} = \text{mes } v$. For the description of random structure of composite let us introduce a conditional density of a probably $\phi(v_m | x_m; x_1, \dots, x_n)$, which is a conditional distribution of the m -th inclusion in the domain v_m at fixed inclusion in the domains v_1, \dots, v_n . As regards the function $\phi(v_m | x_m; x_1, \dots, x_n)$ it is known that $\phi(v_m | x_m; v_1, \dots, v_n) = 0$ at volume of x_m lying inside the domains $v_i \supset v_j$ ($i=1, \dots, n$) united with the characteristic functions V_j^0 and $\phi(v_m | x_m; x_1, \dots, x_n) = \phi(v_m)$ at $|x_i - x_m| \rightarrow \infty, i=1, \dots, n$.

The overall response of the medium is defined by reference to a displacement boundary conditions

$$u(x) = \varepsilon^0 x, \quad x \in \partial w,$$

where ε^0 is a constant symmetric tensor.

The effective parameter L^{s*} in the macromedium state equations

$$\langle \sigma \rangle = L^{s*} \langle \varepsilon \rangle \quad (2.8)$$

are defined by relation

$$L^{s*} = \langle L^s A^{s*} \rangle, \quad (2.9)$$

where the tensor A^{s*} is found from the solution of elastic problem $\varepsilon(x) = A^{s*}(x) \langle \varepsilon \rangle$. Here and below the superscript s indicates the calculation of the value under examination with the help of L^s .

3. THE EVALUATING OF EFFECTIV PARAMETER L^{S*}

3.1. General integral relation

Secant modulus concept realization for evaluation L^{S*} is, in this instance, equivalent to solving of nonlinear elastic problem of composite mechanics with examination of the EFM linear variant at each step. For this reason only short EFM outline will be presented in this paper (comprehensive data contains in Buryachenko and Parton [1]).

Substituting of local equation for the material state

$$\sigma(x) = L^S(x)\varepsilon(x) \quad (3.1)$$

in the equilibrium equation $\nabla\sigma=0$, we obtain an integral equation (Buryachenko and Lipanov [2])

$$\varepsilon(x) = \langle \varepsilon \rangle + \int U^S(x-y) \{ L_1^S(y)\sigma(y) - \langle L_1^S \sigma \rangle \} dy, \quad (3.2)$$

where $U^S(x-y) = \nabla\nabla G^S(x-y)$, G^S - the Green tensor of the Lamé's equation of a homogeneous medium with an elastic modulus tensor $L^{S(0)}$. In (3.2) and below $\langle \cdot \rangle$, $\langle \cdot | x_1, \dots, x_n; x_{n+1}, \dots, x_m \rangle$ stand for the average and the conditional average taken from the ensemble of a statistically homogeneous ergodic field X , on condition that there are inclusions at the points x_1, \dots, x_n and $x_1, \dots, x_n \neq x_{n+1}, \dots, x_m$; $\langle \cdot \rangle_k$ is the volume average involving the ellipsoid v_k .

By way of conditional statistical averaging (with the help of various distribution functions $\Phi(v_m | x_m; x_1, \dots, x_n)$), the problem of evaluation of the effective parameters of the medium is reduced to an infinite system of integral equations ($n=1, \dots$)

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle \varepsilon | x_1, \dots, x_n \rangle - \\ & - \sum_{i=1}^N \int U^S(x-y) v_i(y) \langle L_1^S(y)\varepsilon(y) | x_1, \dots, x_n \rangle dy = \langle \varepsilon \rangle + \\ & + \int U^S(x-y) \{ \langle L_1^S(y)\varepsilon(y) | y; x_1, \dots, x_n \rangle - \langle L_1^S \varepsilon \rangle \} dy \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

Let us denote the right-hand member of the n -th line of the system by the field $\hat{\varepsilon}(x)_{1, \dots, n}$, then each inclusion v_i ($i=1, \dots, n$) of the chosen fixed inclusions is in nonhomogeneous field ($j=1, \dots, n; j \neq i; x \in v_i$)

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_i(x) = \hat{\varepsilon}(x)_{1, \dots, n} + \sum_{j \neq i} \int U^S(x-y) v_j(y) L_1^S(y)\varepsilon(y) dy \quad (3.4)$$

3.2. The effective field

Let us apply the EFM (Buryachenko and Lipanov [2], Buryachenko [3]) hypotheses to close and subsequently solve approximately system (3.4):

H1) Each inclusion v_i has an ellipsoidal form, located in the homogeneous field $\bar{\varepsilon}(x)$ and $(x \in v_i, \bar{v}_i = \text{mes} v_i)$

$$\int U^s(x-y) V_i(y) L_i^s(y) \varepsilon(y) dy = \langle U^s(x-y) \rangle_i \langle L_i^s(y) \varepsilon(y) \rangle_i \bar{v}_i$$

H2) At some sufficiently big n there occurs a closure $\langle \hat{\varepsilon}(x)_{1, \dots, j, n+1} \rangle = \langle \hat{\varepsilon}(x)_{1, \dots, n} \rangle_i$, where the righthand member of the equality does not contain the index $j \neq i$, $1 < j < n$ and $x \in v_j$.

Due to linearity of problem, there exist constant fourth-rank tensor A_i^s such that

$$\langle \varepsilon(x) \rangle_i = A_i^s \langle \bar{\varepsilon}(x) \rangle_i, \quad (3.5)$$

$$\bar{v}_i \langle L_i^s(x) \sigma(x) \rangle = R_i^s \langle \bar{\varepsilon}(x) \rangle_i,$$

where $R_i^s = \bar{v}_i P_i^s (I - A_i^s)$, $P_i^s = -\langle \nabla \nabla G^s(x-y) \rangle_i$, $(x, y \in v_i)$. For example, for the homogeneous ellipsoidal domain v_i with $L_i^s(x) = L_i^{s(t)} = \text{const}$, $A_i^s = (1 + P_i^s L_i^{s(t)})^{-1}$.

3.3. The evaluation of L^{s*}

System (3.4) can be solved by analytical methods, if

$$\langle \hat{\varepsilon}(x)_{1,2} \rangle_i = \langle \bar{\varepsilon}(x) \rangle_i = \text{const}. \quad (i=1,2) \quad (3.6)$$

Then from (3.3), taking account of (3.5), (3.6), we get the expression for effective parameters

$$L^{s*} = L^{s(0)} + \sum_{i=1}^N R_i^s D_i^s n_i, \quad D_i^s = R_i^{s-1} \sum_{j=1}^N Y_{ij}^s R_j^s, \quad (3.7)$$

where n_q is a calculated concentration of inhomogeneous, matrix Y^{-1} has elements $(Y^{-1})_{ij}$ ($i, j=1, \dots, N$) in the form of submatrices (6*6)

$$(Y^{-1})_{ij} = \delta_{ij} [I - R_i^s \sum_{i=1}^N T_{iq}^s(x_i - x_q) Z_{qi}^s \Phi(v_q | x_q; x_i) dx_q] - \quad (3.8)$$

$$- R_i^s \int [T_{ij}^s(x_i - x_j) Z_{ji}^s \Phi(v_j | x_j; x_i) - T_i^s(x_i - x_j) n_j] dx_j$$

$$(Z^s)_{ji}^{-1} = I \delta_{ji} - (1 - \delta_{ji}) T_{ji}^s(x_j - x_i) R_i^s,$$

$$T_{ji}^s(x_j - x_i) = (\bar{v}_j \bar{v}_i)^{-1} \iint U^s(x-y) V_j(x) V_i(y) dx dy$$

$$T_i^s(x_i - x_j) = \bar{v}_i^{-1} \int U^s(x-x_j) V_i(x) dx$$

The relationships (3.7), (3.8) is obtained for any degree of components' anisotropy. Tensor R_i^s ($i=1,2,\dots$) determines concentration of polarisation tensor on isolated inclusion within the unbounded matrix, and tensor D_i^s ($i=1,2,\dots$) describes the contribution to strains concentration in the vicinity of inclusion of other inclusions effects $\langle \bar{\epsilon} \rangle_i = D_i^s \langle \epsilon \rangle$.

3.4. Average strains and field fluctuation in components

The average field of elastic strains inside inclusions $\langle \epsilon \rangle_i$ and matrix $\langle \epsilon \rangle_0$ is determined by expressions

$$\langle \epsilon \rangle_i = A_i^s D_i^s \langle \epsilon \rangle, \quad (i=1,2,\dots) \quad (3.9)$$

$$\langle \epsilon \rangle_0 = c_0^{-1} (\langle \epsilon \rangle - \langle \epsilon V \rangle),$$

Fourth-rank tensor of the second moment of strains $\langle \epsilon \otimes \epsilon \rangle_i$ averaged by the component v_i volume, is exactly determined by Parton and Buryachenko [7] from functional dependence $L^{s*} = L^{s*}(L^{s(i)})$

$$\langle \epsilon_{kl} \epsilon_{mn} \rangle_i = c_i^{-1} \partial L_{pqrs}^{s*} / \partial L_{klmn}^{s(i)} \langle \epsilon_{pq} \rangle \langle \epsilon_{rs} \rangle, \quad (c_i \equiv \langle V_i \rangle) \quad (3.10)$$

Relation (3.10) has been gained for any degree of anisotropy $L^{s*}, L^{s(i)}$ ($i=0,1,\dots$); for isotropic tensor $L^{s(i)} = (3k^{s(i)}, 2\mu^{s(i)})$ ($i=0,1,\dots$) we will have

$$\langle \epsilon_{00}^2 \rangle_i = (9c_i)^{-1} \partial L_{mnpq}^{s*} / \partial k^{s(i)} \langle \epsilon_{mn} \rangle \langle \epsilon_{pq} \rangle, \quad (3.11)$$

$$\langle \epsilon_{kl} \epsilon_{kl} \rangle_i = (2c_i)^{-1} \partial L_{mnpq}^{s*} / \partial \mu^{s(i)} \langle \epsilon_{mn} \rangle \langle \epsilon_{pq} \rangle.$$

4. THE ESTIMATING OF THE SECANT MODULUS L^S

The problem of a nonlinear elastic composites even at a local level is substantially nonlinear one because of nonlinear dependence between strains and stress. Widely distributed method of linearization in nonlinear elasticity problems assumes homogeneity the field of stresses or deformations when computing material tensors, which describe nonlinear effects. One usually ([5]-[6]) equate to terms ($i=0,1,\dots$)

$$L(x) = L^{S(i)} \equiv L(x, \langle \varepsilon_o \rangle_i^2, \langle \vartheta_{kl} \rangle_i \langle \vartheta_{kl} \rangle_i), \quad x \in v_i \quad (4.1)$$

The hypothesis (4.1) is inconsistent. In fact, let us consider an isotropical porous material with matrix, elastic properties of which are described by the strain potential (2.5). In this case under hydrostatic loading condition $\langle \varepsilon_{ij} \rangle = \langle \varepsilon_o \rangle \delta_{ij}$, irrespective of microstructure of pores and the method of calculation of $\langle \varepsilon \rangle_o$ (for example by the formula (3.10) or any other formula) we obtain, that $\langle \vartheta \rangle_o = 0$. It means that this porous materials has only linear elastic deformations at hydrostatic compression.

The above mentioned inconsistency is possible to be avoided if according to (3.11) the linearization condition

$$L(x) = L^{S(i)} \equiv L(x, \langle \varepsilon_o^2 \rangle_i, \langle \vartheta^2 \rangle_i), \quad x \in v_i, \quad i=0,1,\dots \quad (4.2)$$

will be met. Here $\langle \varepsilon_o^2 \rangle_i, \langle \vartheta^2 \rangle_i$ ($i=0,1,\dots$) are defined by (3.11).

Since the secant modulus $L^{S(i)}$ (and consievently L^{S*}) are not known a priori, an iterative procedure is usually required. We may start by assuming

$$L^{S(i)(0)} \equiv L^{(i)}(x, 0, 0), \quad x \in v_i, \quad i=0,1,\dots \quad (4.3)$$

and calculate the corresponding $L^{S*(0)}$ and $\langle \varepsilon_o^2 \rangle_i^{(0)}, \langle \vartheta^2 \rangle_i^{(0)}$ ($i=0,1,\dots$) by equations (3.7) and (3.11) accordingly. The other secant modulus then follows from equations

$$L^{S(i)(n)} = L(x, \langle \varepsilon_o^2 \rangle_i^{(n-1)}, \langle \vartheta^2 \rangle_i^{(n-1)}) \quad , \quad x \in v_i, \quad i=0,1,\dots, n=1,2,\dots$$

Where n is the number of an iteration, $\langle \varepsilon_o^2 \rangle_i^{(n-1)}, \langle \vartheta^2 \rangle_i^{(n-1)}$ are defined by (3.11) at $L^{S*} = L^{S*(n-1)}, L^{S(i)} = L^{S(i)(n-1)}$. If

$\|L - L^{S*(n)} / L^{S*(n-1)}\| \equiv \xi \ll 1$ the solution is found; usually $n \leq 5$ at $\xi = 10^{-2}$.

5. ANALITICAL RESULT

Let us consider, as an example, the problem of evaluating the effective parameter L^{S*} of the composite media with spherical pores

($a^1=a^2=a^3=a$) in matrix with the elastic properties (2.6)

$$L^{(o)}=C^{(o)}+\psi^{(o)}, \quad C^{(o)}=(\infty, 2\mu^{(o)}), \quad \psi^{(o)}=(0, \gamma e^2) \quad (5.1)$$

According to (3.7), (5.1) it turns out that

$$L^{s*}=C^*+\psi^*, \quad (5.2)$$

$$C^*=(4\mu^{(o)}[1/c-29/24], 2\mu^{(o)}[1-35c/24]/[1+5c/24]) \quad (5.3)$$

Relation (5.3) obtained for additional assumptions ($i, j=1, 2, \dots, n$)

$$Z_{ij}^s = I\delta_{ij} + (I - \delta_{ij}) \nabla \nabla G(x_i - x_j) R_j^s, \quad \phi(v_j | x_j; x_i) = (1 - v_i^o) n_j \quad (5.4)$$

where v_i^o is a sphere. The tensor ψ^* obtained from linearisation conditions (4.1) and (4.2) are given by (accordingly)

$$\psi^* = \gamma(0, (1-c)f_2^2 \langle e^2 \rangle) \quad (5.5)$$

$$\psi^* = \gamma(16f_1^2 \langle \varepsilon_o \rangle^2 + 2f_1 f_2 \langle e \rangle^2, 8f_1 f_2 \langle \varepsilon_o \rangle^2 + f_2^2 \langle e \rangle^2), \quad (5.6)$$

where $f_1 \equiv (1/c - 29/24)(1-c)^{-1/2}$, $f_2 \equiv (24 - 35c)(24 + 5c)^{-1}(1-c)^{-1/2}$, $\langle e \rangle^2 \equiv 4 \langle \varepsilon_{ij} \rangle \langle \varepsilon_{ij} \rangle / 3$. The nonlinear deformation $\langle \varepsilon_o^2 \rangle$ (5.6) will also occur under hydrostatic compression which contradicts to the conventional deformation of composites based on the assumed homogeneity of the field of strains in the matrix (5.5).

References

1. Buryachenko V.A., Parton V.Z., *Effective field method in statics of composites*, J. Appl. Mech. & Tech. Phys., Vol. 33, No. 5, pp. 129-140, 1992. (In Russian)
2. Buryachenko V.A., Lipanov A.M., *Stress concentration at ellipsoidal inclusions and effective thermoelastic properties of composite materials*, Soviet Applied Mech., Vol. 22, No. 11, pp. 1103-1109, 1986.
3. Buryachenko V.A., *Correlation function of stress field in matrix composites*, Mechanics of Solids, Vol. 22, No. 3, pp. 66-73, 1987.
4. Willis J.R., Tadmor G.J., *Variational methods in the theory of random composite materials*, In: Continuum models and discrete systems (Maugin G.A., ed.) Longman Scientific & Technical, London 1992, Vol. 1, pp. 113-131.
5. Tandon G.P., Weng G.J., *A theory of particle-reinforced plasticity*, J. Appl. Mech., Vol. 55, No. 1, pp. 126-135, 1988.
6. Buryachenko V.A., Lipanov A.M., *Effective characteristics of elastic physically nonlinear composites*, Soviet Appl. Mech., Vol. 26, No. 1, pp. 9-13, 1990.
7. Parton V.Z., Buryachenko V.A., *A stress fluctuation in elastic composites*, Sov. Phys. Dokl., Vol. 35, No. 2, pp. 191-193, 1990.

FILAMENT WINDING
